

Theoretical Foundations And Optimization Techniques For Learning Mathematics In Data Science And Machine Learning.

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Abstract- Mathematics is a fundamental component of Data Science, providing the theoretical foundations for many data analysis and Machine learning techniques. A breakdown of the fundamental math field required for data Science, Linear Algebra, Calculus, and Probability Theory. Through mathematics we can learn data analysis and visualization in this we learn plotting, charting and data storytelling.in this Article we discussed structuring and designing of mathematics in data science this provides a Comprehensive framework for understanding the mathematical foundations. Data analysis and visualizations, machine learning And modeling, and mathematical techniques used in data science. Being a data scientist is more than just using plug-and- play machine learning packages. Educators have to understand what the algorithm is actually doing first and foremost and know when and why to use it. The process to learn what the algorithms are doing is by studying the underlying mathematics. We know that Geometry and graph theory form essential pillars of data science, it providing tools to model, analyze, and visualize complex relationship. These mathematical concepts enable data scientists to efficiently uncover patterns, optimize systems, and efficiently represent intricate datasets. Now, I know “Big Data” and “Hadoop” have become a bit of a big deal in the data world and are being thrown around like a cool fad, but it feels like a lot of people still don’t really understand the concept behind it. In this article I’ve covered the why and what of Open-source software how does it all actually work? Data is essential for ML-enabled systems. Poor data will result in inaccurate predictions, which are referred to in the ML context as “garbage in, garbage out”. Hence, ML requires high-quality input data. From the viewpoint of RE, it is clear that data constitutes a new type of requirements Based on the Data Quality model defined in the standard ISO/IEC 25012, we elaborate on the data Perspective.

Keywords- Mathematical Foundations, Data Analysis and Visualization, Optimization, Machine Learning, Modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data science is a multidisciplinary field that combines mathematics, statistics, computer science, and domain expertise to extract. Mathematics is a fundamental component of Data Science, providing the theoretical foundations for many data Analysis and Machine learning techniques. A breakdown of the Fundamental math field required for data Science, Linear Algebra, Calculus, And Probability Theory. Here we discussed how to structuring and designing of mathematics in data science.in this article, I want to details the math’s you actually need for data science and exactly the things you should study, along with Useful resources. Now, data science is a big field, and the job itself is still not clearly defined. Data scientists at different Companies often have slightly different roles, so the math’s required for each position will ultimately vary. However, there are some fundamental topics, in my opinion, all data scientists should know and will likely cover the majority of requirements in job

Description and questions you may get asked in Interviews. Becoming a Machine Learning (ML) engineer can be a thrilling and Rewarding journey. In today’s industry, ML is at the core of AI, powering everything from recommendation systems to self- Driving cars. However, many aspiring ML engineers often wonder, “How much math do I really need?” While deep knowledge of mathematics is a powerful asset, the good news is you don’t need a PhD in math to start working in the ML field. What’s Essential knows the key mathematical concepts that directly impact your work. In this article, I’ll break down the minimum Mathematics you need to learn to work as an ML engineer in 2024, and more importantly, where and how these concepts are applied in real-world.

II . Optimization Techniques:

optimization techniques are fundamental in data science. They provide a mathematical Framework for minimizing errors, improving accuracy, and efficiently tuning models. These

methods form the basis of many Machine learning algorithms. [2] An optimization problem focuses on identifying the optimal solution for specific objective Function, which involves minimizing costs and errors or maximizing efficiency.

Types of Optimization Problems:

- 1). **Constrained vs. Unconstrained:** Problems may include restrictions (e.g. Resource limits) or allow freedom in parameter Selection.
- 2). **Linear vs. Nonlinear:** Objective functions and constraints can be linear or nonlinear,
- 3). **Integer and Mixed Variables:** Decision variables can be continuous, integers, or a mix of both.

Optimization Techniques:

- 1). Gradient Descent: A widely used methods to iteratively adjust parameters by following the gradient of the objective function to minimize errors. The key variants include.
- 2). Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD): Reduces computation using random samples instead of the entire dataset.
- 3). Conjugate Gradient Method (CGM): Combine first – order efficiency with second-order accuracy for large – scale problems.
- 4). Derivative –Free Methods (DFM): It uses genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization to solve problems without explicit derivatives.
- 5). Zeros –Order Optimization: (ZOO): This algorithm efficiently approximates derivatives for problems where gradient are Hard to Compute.
- Programming assignments a bit easier focus more on the problem to be solved than on programming

Knapsack Problem in Optimization:

You are about to sit down to a dinner. [4] you know how much you value different foods, e.g., you like donuts more than 750 calories. Choosing what to eat is a knapsack problem. A vector, V , of length, is used to indicate whether or not items are taken. If $V[i]=1$, then $L[i]$ taken... If $V[i]=0$, item $L[i]$ is not taken. How many possible different values can V have? As many different binary numbers as can be represented in n bits.

Examples: if there are 100 items to choose from, the power set is of Size?

1. Each item is represented by a pair, (Value, weight) 2.The knapsack can accommodate items with a total weight of no more than W . 3. A vector L , of length n , represents the set of available items. Each element of the vector is an item. 4. A vector V , of length, is used to indicate whether or not items are taken. If $V[i]=1$, then $L[i]=1$ is taken. If $V[i]=0$, item $L[i]$ is not taken

"Figure 1. Knapsack problem Food items".

Brute Force Algorithm

- 1).Enumerate all possible combinations of items. That is to say, generate all subsets of the set of items This is called the power set.
 - 2).Remove all of the combinations whose total units exceed the allowed weight.
 - 3).From the remaining combinations choose any one whose value is the largest. Knapsack problem Formalized
- Find a V that maximizes $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} V[i] * I[i]$. Value
Subject to the constraint that $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} V[i] * I[i]$. Weight. $\leq w$

"Figure 2. Methods of Optimization".

Figure ; 3 Three Pillars of Data Figure Science”.

“Figure 4. Machine Learning”

“2” Mathematics is the foundation of machine learning. Math concepts play a crucial role in understanding how models learn from data and optimizing their performance.

- Math provides the theoretical foundation for understanding how machine learning algorithms work.
- Concepts like calculus and linear algebra enable fine-tuning of models for better performance.
- Knowing the math helps troubleshoot issues in models and algorithms.
- Topics like deep learning, NLP and reinforcement learning require strong mathematical foundations.

Before diving into machine learning algorithms, it's important to familiarize yourself with foundational topics, like Statistics, Probability Distributions, Linear Algebra, Matrix Operations, Regression, Geometry, Dimensionality Reduction and Vector Calculus.

Linear Algebra and Matrix Operations

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical method for understanding relationships between variables. It is crucial for predictive modeling and interpreting patterns in data. Techniques like linear regression provide the foundation for supervised learning, where the goal is to predict continuous outcomes.

Linear Regression in Machine learning

Linear regression is a type of Supervised machine learning algorithm that learns from the labeled datasets and maps the data points with most optimized linear functions which can be used for prediction on new datasets. It assumes that there is a linear relationship between the input and output, meaning the output changes at a constant rate as the input changes. This relationship is represented by a straight line.

For example we want to predict a student's exam score based on how many hours they studied. We observe that as students study more hours, their scores go up. In the example of predicting exam scores based on hours studied. Here

- Independent variable (input): Hours studied because it's the factor we control or observe.
- Dependent variable (output): Exam scores because it depends on how many hours were studied.

Importance of Regression

Simplicity and Interpretability: It's easy to understand and interpret, making it a starting point for learning about machine learning.

- Predictive Ability: Helps predict future outcomes based on past data, making it useful in various fields like finance, healthcare and marketing.
- Basis for Other Models: Many advanced algorithms, like logistic regression or neural networks, build on the concepts of linear regression.
 - **Efficiency:** It's computationally efficient and works well for problems with a linear relationship.
 - **Widely Used:** It's one of the most widely used techniques in both statistics and machine learning for regression tasks.
 - **Analysis:** It provides insights into relationships between variables (e.g., how much one variable influences another).

Logistic Regression in Machine Learning

In our previous discussion, we explored the fundamentals of machine learning and walked through a hands-on implementation of Linear Regression. Now, let's take a step forward and dive into one of the first and most widely used classification algorithms — Logistic Regression.

What is Logistic Regression?

Logistic regression is a supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification tasks where the goal is to predict the probability that an instance belongs to a given class or not. Logistic regression is a statistical algorithm which analyzes the relationship between two data factors. The article explores the fundamentals of logistic regression, its types and implementations.

Logistic regression is used for binary Classification where we use sigmoid function. that takes input as independent variables and produces a probability value between 0 and 1.

For example, we have two classes Class 0 and Class 1 if the value of the logistic function for an input is greater than 0.5 (threshold value) then it belongs to Class 1 otherwise it belongs to Class 0. It's referred to as regression because it is the extension of linear regression. But is mainly used for classification problems.

Key Points:

- Logistic regression predicts the output of a categorical dependent variable. Therefore, the outcome must be a categorical or discrete value.
- It can be either Yes or No, 0 or 1, true or False, etc. but instead of giving the exact value as 0 and 1, it gives the probabilistic values which lie between 0 and 1.
- In Logistic regression, instead of fitting a regression line, we fit an "S" shaped logistic function, which predicts two maximum values (0 or 1).

Types of Logistic Regression

On the basis of the categories, Logistic Regression can be classified into three types:

- **Binomial:** In binomial Logistic regression, there can be only two possible types of the dependent variables, such as 0 or 1, Pass or Fail, etc.
- **Multinomial:** In multinomial Logistic regression, there can be 3 or more possible unordered types of the dependent variable, such as "cat", "dogs", or "sheep"
- **Ordinal:** In ordinal Logistic regression, there can be 3 or more possible ordered types of dependent variables, such as "low", "Medium", or "High".

Assumptions of Logistic Regression

We will explore the assumptions of logistic regression as understanding these assumptions is important to ensure that we are using appropriate application of the model. The assumption includes:

- **Independent observations:** Each observation is independent of the other. meaning there is no correlation between any input variables.
- **Binary dependent variables:** It takes the assumption that the dependent variable must be binary or dichotomous, meaning it can take only two values. For more than two categories Soft ax functions are used.
- **Linearity relationship between independent variables and log odds:** The relationship between the independent variables and the log odds of the dependent variable should be linear.
- **No outliers:** there should be any outliers in the dataset.
- **Large sample size:** The sample size is sufficiently large

Understanding Sigmoid Function

So far, we've covered the basics of logistic regression, but now let's focus on the most important function that forms the core of logistic regression.

- 1).The sigmoid function is a mathematical function used to map the predicted values to probabilities.
- 2).It maps any real value into another value within a range of 0 and 1. The value of the logistic regression must be between 0 and 1, which cannot go beyond this limit, so it forms a curve like the "S" form.
- 3).The S-form curve is called the sigmoid function or the logistic function.
- 4).In logistic regression, we use the concept of the threshold value, which defines the probability of either 0 or 1. Such as values above the threshold value tends to 1, and a value below the threshold values tends to 0.

How does Logistic Regression work?

The logistic regression model transforms the linear regression function continuous value output into categorical value output using a sigmoid function, which maps any real-valued set of independent variables input into a value between 0 and 1. This function is known as the logistic function.

Let the independent input features be:

$$X = [x_{11} \dots x_{1m} x_{21} \dots x_{2m} \dots x_{n1} \dots x_{nm}]$$

and the dependent variable is Y having only binary value i.e. 0 or 1.

$$Y = \{0 \text{ if Class1} \quad 1 \text{ if Class2}\}$$

then, apply the multi-linear function to the input variables X.

$$z = (\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i) + b$$

Here x_i is the i th observation of X, $w_i = [w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_m]$ is the weights or Coefficient, and b is the bias term also known as intercept. Simply this can be represented as the dot product of weight and bias.

$$z = w \cdot X + b$$

Sigmoid Function

Now we use the sigmoid function where the input will be z and we find the probability between 0 and 1. I.e. predicted y.

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

Binomial Logistic regression:

Target variable can have only 2 possible types: “0” or “1” which may represent “win” vs “loss”, “pass” vs “fail”, “dead” vs “alive”, etc., in this case, sigmoid functions are used, which is already discussed above.

Importing necessary libraries based on the requirement of model. This Python code shows how to use the breast cancer dataset to implement a Logistic Regression model for classification.

```

from sklearn.datasets import load_breast_cancer
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
#load the following dataset
X, y = load_breast_cancer(return_X_y=True)
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test
size=0.20, random state=23)
clf = LogisticRegression(max_iter=10000, random state=0)
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
arc = accuracy_score(y_test, clf.predict(X_test)) * 100
print (logistic Regression model accuracy: {acc:.2f}%)

```

• **Output:**

Logistic Regression model accuracy (in %): 96.49%
This code loads the breast cancer dataset from scikit-learn, splits it into training and testing sets, and then trains a Logistic Regression model on the training data. The model is used to predict the labels for the test data, and the accuracy of these predictions is calculated by comparing the predicted values with the actual labels from the test set. Finally, the accuracy is printed as a percentage.

Multinomial Logistic Regression:

Target variable can have 3 or more possible types which are not ordered (i.e. types have no quantitative significance) like “disease A” vs “disease B” vs “disease C”.

In this case, the soft ax function is used in place of the sigmoid function. Soft ax function for K classes will be:

$$\text{softmax}(z_i) = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}$$

Here, K represents the number of elements in the vector z, and i, j iterates over all the elements in the vector.

Then the probability for class c will be:

$$P(Y=c|X=x) = \frac{e^{w_c \cdot x + b_c}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{w_k \cdot x + b_k}}$$

In Multinomial Logistic Regression, the output variable can have more than two possible

• **Output:**

Logistic Regression model accuracy (in %): 96.66%

How to Evaluate Logistic Regression Model?

So far, we’ve covered the implementation of logistic regression. Now, let’s dive into the evaluation of logistic regression and understand why it’s important

Evaluating the model helps us assess the model’s performance and ensure it generalizes well to new data

We can evaluate the logistic regression model using the following metrics:

- **Accuracy:** Accuracy provides the proportion of correctly classified instances.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TruePositives} + \text{TrueNegatives}}{\text{Total}}$$
- **Precision:** Precision focuses on the accuracy of positive predictions.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TruePositives}}{\text{TruePositives} + \text{FalsePositives}}$$
- **Recall (Sensitivity or True Positive Rate):** Recall measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances among all actual positive instances.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TruePositives}}{\text{TruePositives} + \text{FalseNegatives}}$$
- **F1 Score:** F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$
- **Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC):** The ROC curve plots the true positive rate against the false positive rate at various thresholds. AUC-ROC measures the area under this curve, providing an aggregate measure of a model’s performance across different classification thresholds.
- **Area under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR):** Similar to AUC-ROC, AUC-PR measures the area under the precision-recall curve, providing a summary of a model’s performance across different precision-recall trade-offs.

iii . Conclusion

I found it very helpful for organizing my approach to refreshing my math skills. An understanding of basic optimization techniques and their fundament properties provides important grounding for students Researchers and practitioners in this area. The success of data science and ML-enabled systems involves understanding business context and problems, translating them into ML tasks, designing and experimenting with algorithms, evaluating models, implementing telemetry, among other tasks.

This needs to be considered from early stages of ML software development. We presented our work towards an approach for specifying ML-enabled systems considering five different perspectives: objectives, UX, infrastructure, model, and data. The main contribution of this paper is to provide two new artifacts that can be used to help specifying ML-enabled systems. (i) The perspective-based data science and ML task and concern diagram and (ii) the ML requirements specification template. We believe that these artifacts can help requirements engineers with an overview of ML concerns that should be analyzed together with business owners, designers, software engineers, and data scientists to specify ML-enabled systems.

Future work includes exploring how traditional and new RE techniques can use the perspective-based ML task and concern diagram and the ML specification template. In addition, we plan to conduct empirical studies to evaluate the completeness and feasibility of using the artifacts presented in this work.

Abbreviations

- SGD: Stochastic Gradient Descent
- CGM: Conjugate Gradient Method
- DFM: Derivative –Free Methods
- ZOO: Zeros –Order Optimization

Conflicts of Interest

“The authors declare no conflicts of interest”

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